

Chemical Investigation of the bark of *Tecomella undulata*. Isolation of a New Ester Glucoside, *Tecominn*

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A new ester glucoside, veratroyl β -D-glucoside, named as *Tecominn*, has been isolated from the bark of *Tecomella undulata* together with C_{27} and C_{29} alkanes, C_{28} and C_{30} alkanols and β -sitosterol.

*Tecomella undulata*¹ (G. Don) Seem. (Bignoniaceae: *Rakta-Rohitaka*) is a small tree distributed in Punjab, Waziristan, Baluchistan, Rajasthan, Kathiawar, Gujrat and the Deccan. In view of various uses of *T. undulata* and the occurrence of lapachol² in heartwood of the plant, it was of interest to undertake the present work. The petroleum extract of the bark after saponification and chromatographic resolution over alumina yielded three different types of compounds viz., alkane, alkanol and β -sitosterol, having different R_F values. The alkane, m.p. 60–62°, R_F 1.0, shows no absorption due to OH group in the I.R. spectrum, but shows absorptions at 725 and 735 cm^{-1} due to methylene chain rocking in solid phase. The NMR spectrum shows only one strong peak at 1.25 δ due to methylene protons. The mass spectrum shows prominent peaks 14 mass units apart at 422 (8%), 408 (100%), 394 (25%), 380 (100%), 366 (8%), 352 (10%), and then fragment ion peaks corresponding to C_nH_{2n+1} with maximum intensity at $n = 3, 4, 5$ and 6. These peaks are accompanied by smaller peaks 1 mass unit higher and 1, 2, or 3 mass units lower. The fragmentation pattern³ of the mass spectrum indicates that the alkane is a mixture of *n*-heptacosane, $C_{27}H_{56}$ (M 380) and *n*-nonacosane, $C_{29}H_{60}$ (M 408) with traces of *n*-triacontane, $C_{30}H_{62}$ (M 422). The alkanol, m.p. 81–83°, R_F 0.47, shows IR absorptions at 3350 (OH), and 722 and 734 cm^{-1} (methylene chain rocking). The NMR spectrum shows a prominent peak at 1.25 δ due to methylene protons and small peaks at 3.65 δ (OH). The mass spectrum exhibits prominent higher mass peaks at m/e 448 (3%), 434 (8%), 420 (85%), 406 (58%), 392 (100%), 378 (35%), 364 (60%), and then smaller fragment ion peaks, consistent with the fragmentation sequence $M - (18 + n \cdot 14)$, n being 0, 1, 2, 3, ..., etc. of long chain alcohols. An analysis³ of the mass spectrum indicates that the alkanol is a mixture of *n*-octacosanol, $C_{28}H_{58}O$ (M 410) and *n*-triacontanol, $C_{30}H_{62}O$ (M 438) with traces of *n*-dotriacontanol, $C_{32}H_{66}O$ (M 466). The sterol was identified as β -sitosterol by comparison of rotation and m.p. of the sterol (M^+ 414), its acetate and benzoate with those of an authentic sample⁴.

1. K. R. Kiritkar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. 3, p. 1841, L. M. Basu, Allahabad, India, 1933; I. C. Chopra, K. K. Handa, and L. D. Kapur, "Indigenous Drugs of India", 2nd ed., p. 527, U. N. Dhur and Sons Ltd., Calcutta, India, 1958.
2. S. R. Gupta, K. K. Malik and T. R. Seshadri, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 457
3. H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, "Structure Elucidation of Natural Products", Vol. II, p. 165, Holden-Day Inc., 1964; *idem.*, "Interpretation of Mass Spectra of Organic Compounds", p. 35, Holden-Day, Inc., 1965.
4. "Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry", p. 1808, Elsevier Publishing Co., Inc., 1940.

The chloroform extract of the defatted bark of *T. undulata* afforded a new glucoside, $C_{15}H_{20}O_9$, m.p. 218–220°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -178$ (Pyridine), R_F 0.48. In the mass spectrum the glucoside did not give a molecular ion peak as it did not volatilise at low temperature. At higher temperature (260°) the sample probably decomposed. The NMR spectrum could not be scanned as the glucoside was sparingly soluble in water. The IR spectrum in nujol shows significant absorption bands at 3400 ~ 3200 (strong and broad due to polymeric OH), and 1720 cm^{-1} (Ar-CO-O-). The glucoside on hydrolysis with dilute alkali yielded glucose and an acid, $C_9H_{10}O_4$, m.p. 180–182°. IR spectrum of the acid in nujol shows a strong peak at 1690 cm^{-1} (Ar-COOH), but no peak due to OH absorption. NMR spectrum shows prominent peaks at 3.95 δ (Ar-OME), 6.85 and 6.95 δ (Ar-H) only. Mass spectrum of the acid exhibits a molecular ion peak at m/e 182 together with other significant peaks. An analysis of the spectral data indicated the presence of -COOH and -OMe groups only in the acid, which was subsequently identified as veratric acid by comparison of m.p., mixture m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectrum with an authentic sample. The glucoside does not contain any free reducing group, is sparingly soluble in water due to ester linkage, is easily hydrolysed by emulsion, and exhibits a high negative specific optical rotation.

On the basis of these evidences, the glucoside is assigned the structure (I), veratroyl β -D-glucoside, and is named as *Tecomina*, as it appears to be new.

(I)

With acetic anhydride in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate the glucoside was acetylated to a tetracetyl derivative, $C_{23}H_{28}O_{13}$, m.p. 120–124°, R_F 0.31.

The water soluble portions of the total alcoholic extract of the bark of *T. undulata* as also the chloroform extract of the defatted bark were both found to possess mild relaxant, cardiotoxic and choleric activities on preliminary pharmacological investigations⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points were determined in a sulphuric acid bath in open capillary and are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra in nujol, n.m.r. spectra in chloroform and mass spectra were all run by National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, India.

5. S. K. Bhattacharya, Department of Pharmacology, Institute of Medical Sciences, B.H.U., Varanasi, personal communication.

Thin layer chromatography was conducted on silica gel G impregnated plates using the solvent systems. benzene-chloroform (1 : 1, solvent 1), and chloroform—absolute alcohol (8 : 2, solvent 2). The plates after drying at room temperature were developed either by keeping in a chamber containing iodine vapour, or by spraying with a mixture of acetic anhydride—sulphuric acid—absolute alcohol (5 : 5 : 90% v/v), and then heating at 100–110°.

Descending paper chromatography for carboxylic acid was conducted on Whatman paper No. 1. using the organic phase of mixture of *n*-butanol—1.5 (N) NH₄OH (1 : 1 v/v, solvent 3). The paper was sprayed with an indicator solution consisting of bromothymol blue (100 mg), ethyl alcohol (100 ml) and water (100 ml), the pH of the solution was adjusted with sodium hydroxide to the slightly blue side of its sensitivity range. The carboxylic acid appeared as distinct yellow spot against a bluish background. For the reducing sugars the organic phase of a mixture of *n*-butanol-pyridine-water (30 : 15 : 22.5 v/v, solvent 4) was used as the developer for a descending paper chromatography. After drying in air. the paper was run through a solution of silver nitrate in acetone (2.5%) in a tray and allowed to dry in air. It was then sprayed with an alcoholic NaOH solution (5%), soaked in NH₃-H₂O solution and washed thoroughly with running water. The reducing sugars appeared as deep brown or light yellow spots.

Petroleum-soluble neutral compounds : Dried and milled bark of *T. undulata*⁶ (850 g) was defatted with petroleum (60–80°) in a Soxhlet extractor for about 22 hrs. Removal of solvent yielded a brown gummy mass (3.45 g) which was saponified with strong alcoholic alkali (10 g NaOH, 10 ml. H₂O and 40 ml EtOH) by heating under reflux for 16 hrs. On removal of alcohol the residual solution was extracted with ether (4 × 80 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ and on removal of solvent yielded a yellowish brown crystalline mass (1.0 g) which was a mixture of mainly 3 compounds of R_F 1.0, 0.47 and 0.37, as revealed by TLC (Solvent 1) They were isolated by chromatographic resolution of the mixture over Brockmann neutral alumina (25 g.), and identified as mixtures of C₂₇ and C₂₉—alkanes, C₂₈ and C₃₀—alkanols and β-sitosterol in the following way.

Alkanes : Petroleum (60–80°) eluates yielded a mixture of *n*-heptacosane, C₂₇H₅₆ and *n*-nonacosane, C₂₉H₆₀, with traces of *n*-triacontane, C₃₀H₆₂ (65.7 mg); R_F 1.0 (solvent 1); crystallised from acetone as small needles, m.p. 60–62°; i r. ν_{max}^{nujol} 725 and 735 cm⁻¹ (methylene chain rocking in solid phase), no OH absorption; n.m.r. δ 1.25 (strong peak due to methylene protons); m/e 422 (8%), 408 (100%), 394 (25%), 380 (100%), 366 (8%), 352 (10%) etc. (Found : C, 85.5, 85.7; H, 14.92, 14.62. Calc. for C₂₇H₅₆ : C, 85.17; H, 14.83. C₂₉H₆₀ : C, 85.20; H, 14.80%).

Alkanols : Benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluates afforded a mixture of *n*-octacosanol, C₂₈H₅₈O and *n*-triacontanol, C₃₀H₆₂O, with traces of *n*-dotriacontanol, C₃₂H₆₆O (49.1 mg); R_F 0.47 (solvent 1); crystallised from acetone as granules, m.p. 81–83°; i r. λ_{max}^{nujol} 3350 (OH) and 722 and 734 cm⁻¹ (methylene chain rocking); n.m.r. δ 1.25 (strong peak due to methylene

6. The bark of *T. undulata* was received from Dr. L. D. Kapoor, National Botanic Gardens, Lucknow, India.

protons), and δ 3.65 (OH); m/e 448 (3%), 434 (8%), 420 (85%), 406 (58%), 392 (100%), 378 (35%), 364 (60%) etc. (Found : C, 82.2, 82.2; H, 14.30, 14.00. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{58}O$: C, 81.87; H, 14.23. $C_{30}H_{62}O$: C, 82.11; H, 14.24%).

β -Sitosterol : The chloroform eluates yielded β -sitosterol (0.132 g), m.p. 135–137° (EtOH), $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -36.88 (CHCl₃), R_F 0.37 (Solvent 1), a violet to blue to green colour with Liebermann-Burchard reagent, m/e 414 (M⁺). (Found : C, 81.73, 81.81; H, 12.07, 11.96. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 83.99; H, 12.15%). *Acetate*, m.p. 120–123° (EtOH), $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -30.95 (CHCl₃). (Found : C, 81.8, 82.0; H, 11.42, 11.57. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%). *Benzate*, m.p. 145–146° (EtOH). $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -22.1 (CHCl₃). (Found : C, 83.55, 83.80; H, 10.42, 10.50. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{54}O_2$: C, 83.34; H, 10.49%).

Chloroform-soluble Glycosides : Dried and powdered bark of *T. undulata* (320 g.) was thoroughly defatted with petroleum (60–80°) and then benzene. The defatted material was next extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract on evaporation yielded a dark brown gummy solid (7.95 g) which responded to tests for glycosides, and on thin layer chromatography showed the presence of 3 components, R_F 0.31, 0.48 and 0.61 (solvent 2). A new glucoside, *Tecomina*, was isolated from the mixture in the following way.

Tecomina : The gummy solid was repeatedly extracted with hot absolute alcohol. The combined brown alcoholic extract was heated under reflux with activated charcoal to remove the colouring matters. The filtered light yellow solution on concentration under reduced pressure afforded the glucoside, *Tecomina*, as colourless granules (0.371 g), m.p. 218–220° (EtOH), $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -178 (Pyridine), R_F 0.48 (solvent 2), i.r. ν_{max}^{nujol} 3400 ~ 3200 (strong and broad due to polymeric OH) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (Ar-CO-O-). (Found : C, 52.62, 52.94, 53.22, 52.96; H, 5.99, 5.86, 6.22, 6.100, Calc. for $C_{15}H_{20}O_9$: C, 52.32; H, 5.86%).

Hydrolysis of the glucoside, Tecomin : Tecomin (1.25 g) was dissolved in excess water (200 ml) and heated on steam-bath for 20 min. with alkali (6.6 g NaOH dissolved in 20 ml H₂O, strength of alkali 3%). The mixture was cooled in ice and made acidic to congo with conc. HCl, and then extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract on evaporation afforded an acid (50 mg) (liberated I₂ from KI-KIO₃ mixture), a single spot material of R_F 0.205 (solvent 3) which was identified as veratric acid in the following way.

Veratric acid : The acid was crystallised from acetone as light brown needles, m.p. 180–182°, i.r. ν_{max}^{nujol} 1690 cm⁻¹ (Ar-COOH), but no OH absorption; n.m.r. δ 3.95 (Ar-OMe, prominent), δ 6.85 and δ 6.95 (Ar-H) only; m/e 182 (M⁺), 167 (M-Me), 165 (M-OH), 139 (m/e 167-CO), 137 (M- $\ddot{C} \equiv C$ -OH), 122 (m/e 167-COOH), and 45 ($\ddot{C} \equiv C$ -OH). (Found : C, 60.20; H, 6.23. Calc. for $C_9H_{10}O_4$: C, 59.3; H, 5.4%). The acid was identified as veratric acid by superimposable i.r. spectra and no depression in mixture m.p. with an authentic sample.

Glucose : The acid hydrolysate of Tecomin on paper chromatography exhibited a single spot of R_F 0.32 (solvent 4) on papergram, identical with that of D-glucose. The sugar was further characterised through the formation of osazone.

Hydrolysis of Tecomin with emulsin : An aqueous solution of Tecomin was treated with emulsin at 40°. This solution was spotted on paper along with a blank solution without emulsin at intervals and developed for detection of sugars (solvent 4). The aqueous

solution of Tecomin with emulsin developed a reducing spot identical with that of glucose, whereas the blank solution of Tecomin without emulsin did not exhibit any reducing spot on papergram. This proved that Tecomin does not contain any free reducing group, and has a β -glucosidic linkage.

Acetylation of Tecomin: Tecomin (100 mg) and anhydrous sodium acetate (80 mg) were mixed thoroughly and heated with acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) for 30 min. till clear solution was obtained. The solution was further heated under reflux for another 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed with crushed ice and stirred thoroughly to break up the solid lumps which were collected at the pump and washed thoroughly with water. Crystallisation from ethanol afforded colourless needles of tetraacetyl veratroyl β -D-glucoside (48 mg) m.p. 120–124°, R_f 0.31 (solvent CHCl_3). (Found: C, 53.71, 54.80; H, 4.65, 5.96. Calc. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_{11}$: C, 53.90; H, 5.46%).

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